

Influence of Swine Wastes Rates on Selected Soil Physical Properties and Cultivation of Amaranthus in Awka, South East- Nigeria

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Abstract

Environmental threats most times occur due to indiscriminate disposal of swine wastes into the environment however effective disposal of these waste materials into the soil as an amendment for vegetable production remains a vital solution for the challenge. This research investigated different application rates of swine wastes on selected soil physical properties and cultivation of Amaranthus in Awka. The research was conducted at the Soil Science and Land Resources Management Research and Teaching Farm, Faculty of Agriculture, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka- Nigeria. The field experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design. Soil samples were taken from each plot with core samplers undisturbed and randomly and was taken to the laboratory for soil physical analysis prior to the application of treatment. The treatment used was swine wastes at rates of 0 kg/plot (zero application), 4.5 kg/plot, 9.0 kg/plot and 13.5 kg/plot. The test crop used was *Amaranthus hybridus*. The results obtained from the laboratory were subjected to statistical analysis and the treatment means were separated using Turkey test at 5% probability level. The results showed that the soils of the studied area was sandy loam. There was a significant difference in bulk density when the soil treated with 9.0 kg/plot was compared with 0 kg/plot (zero application) and it ranged from 1.75-1.97 g/cm³, the total porosity of soil in the studied area was significant when the soils treated with 9.0 kg/plot was compared with 0 kg/plot (zero application) and this ranged from 23.5 - 29.59 %, the moisture content of soil in the studied area was significantly different when soils treated with 9.0 kg/plot was compared with 0 kg/plot (zero application) and it ranged from 1.95- 3.22 %. The aggregate stability of soils in the area studied ranged from 0.37- 0.44 %, hydraulic conductivity of soils in the studied area was in the range of 0.01- 0.05 cm/hr. From this research, it was observed that 13.5 kg/plot of swine wastes applied improved the yield of Amaranthus when compared to other treatment rates.

Keywords: Amaranthus, application rates, slurry, soil, swine wastes

Introduction

The use of organic manures for the production of leafy vegetables has been reported to be effective (Iren et al., 2012) and the application of these organic materials as soil nutrients

provides growth-regulating substrates and improves the physical, chemical and microbial properties of the soil (Iren et al., 2015). Most tropical soils are highly susceptible to degradation under continuous cultivation however good quality soil is important for sustainable crop production especially under continuous cultivation. Amaranthus, also called African spinach, Bush green, Green leaf belongs to the family *Amaranthaceae*. They are the most commonly grown leafy vegetable of the lowland tropics in Asia and Africa. Amaranth leaves have wonderful chemical composition with mild spinach-like taste so it comes beneath an accurate leafy vegetable (Amicarelli and Camaggio, 2012). It may be eaten as raw in salad or by cooked along or with other vegetables especially with potato; due to its chemical composition it plays an important role in nutrition (Uusikua et al., 2010). It contains calcium, Magnesium, Carotene and Niacin, Vitamin A and C are also present in significant levels. The protein found in young plants of Amaranths can be important for people without access of meat or other sources of protein thus the need to sustain the cultivation of Amaranthus using adequate manure. Manure from swine production could be an asset to a pork producer and to agriculture in general if properly managed and utilized in a sustainable food production system and because swine manure contains essential plant nutrients, its use as a soil amendment for crop production is a practical method to solve the disposal problem. The composition and effectiveness of swine waste as a source of nutrients depends on several factors including the type of ratio fed, housing system and methods of manure collection, storage and handling. Soil is the dynamic link between the biosphere and the lithosphere and constitutes a practically non-renewable natural resources, with the key role for the environment and for the agriculture (Moraetis et al., 2016). Some factors such as altitude, parent rocks, vegetation and anthropogenic activities influences the physical properties of the soil like soil texture, bulk density and moisture content. Inappropriate disposal of swine wastes into the environment often times leads to environmental pollution which could pose a serious health challenge hence the need to channel these wastes into the soil as an amendment for vegetable production remains a solution to solving the disposal challenge.

Materials and Methods

Description of Experimental Site

The research was carried out at Soil Science and Land Resources Management Teaching and Research farm, Faculty of Agriculture, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka-Nigeria. The research farm is located within latitude 6.244175° N and 6.250008° N and longitude 7.116615° E and 7.117172° E, with an average annual rainfall of 2590.6 mm as per Nigeria meteorological Agency data for the year 2022; the rainfall distribution pattern is bimodal with early rain occurring between April and July and late rain between August and October. It has an average relative humidity range of 76 - 80 % and average maximum and minimum temperatures of 32.1 and 23.5°C respectively. The experimental site has a slight slope with a well-drained soil. The soils of the experimental area can be classified as Ultisols according to USDA soil classification system. Weeds such as *chromolena odorata*, *Aspillia africana*, *panicum maximum* and *cyperus spp* dominated the vegetation of the experimental site.

Experimental Design and Layout

The experiment was conducted in Randomized Completely Block Design (RCBD) with four treatments and three replications. The treatment used was swine wastes applied at the rates of 0kg/plot (Zero Application), 4.5 kg/plot, 9.0 kg/plot and 13.5kg/plot.

Field Operations and Soil Sample collection (pre-planting)

The experimental field size of 14.5 m x 15 m (217.5 Sq./m) was mapped out using a measuring tape, twine rope and pegs. Prior to land clearing, surface soil samples were collected from the experimental plot undisturbed from ten different points using core samplers for physical analysis while soil auger was used to collect soil samples at 20 different points at the depth of 0-20 cm after which it was bulked and mixed thoroughly from which a representative sample was collected. Land clearing was done using a cutlass; the debris were packed in between the furrows. Sixteen (16) plots of 3 m x 3 m (9 Sq./m) each was made using a hoe, the furrows spacing was 0.5 m x 1 m respectively while transplanting spacing used was 0.25m and 0.5m respectively for intra row and inter row respectively

Post planting

After harvest, soil samples for physical analysis were again collected accordingly; both samples collected prior to treatment application and after treatment/ harvest were respectively labelled and bagged for onward laboratory analysis.

Pre Nursery and Nursery Operation

The locally sourced seeds for the experiment were subjected to viability test of which 90 % germination was attained before planting in the nursery. A nursery bed was made very close to the experimental field for ease of transplant and to avoid transplanting shock of the Amaranthus seedlings. The swine wastes sourced from the Animal farm of the faculty of Agriculture was mixed in water to form slurry after which it was applied on the beds before transplanting. The swine wastes was directly applied on the experimental plots one week before transplanting with enough water applied daily to undergo a curing process. The Amaranthus seedlings transplanted had an average height of 0.32 m.

Plant Data Collection

Five middle stands from each plot were tagged and used as sample plants for data collection on the following agronomic properties.

- I. **Average plant height at 3 weeks after transplanting (3WAT):** The plant height was measured using a meter rule from soil level to the apex of the leaves at 3 weeks after transplanting.
- II. **Leaf area index:** The leaf area was measured using a meter rule, it was calculated according to the procedure of Samkeliso et al., 2020
- III. **Fresh shoot weight:** Fresh shoot was harvested and weighed using weighing balance
- IV. **Dry shoot weight:** The fresh shoot was subjected to drying in the oven at a temperature of 105°C for 72 hours until a constant weight was achieved it was weighed again.
- V. **Number of nodes after first and second cut:** The nodes were counted after first and second cut

Laboratory analysis

Particle size Distribution: The hydrometer method as described by Gee and Or 2002 was used to determine the particle size distribution of the samples while the soil textures were determined using the USDA Textural triangle. The bulk density was determined by core method as described by Grossman and Reinsch (2002). Saturated Hydraulic conductivity (k_{sat}) was determined by method of Young (2001). Soil Aggregate stability was determined using wet sieving method of Kemper and Rosenau (1986). Soil Total Porosity was calculated from the bulk density as shown in this equation:

$$\text{Total porosity (\%)} = \frac{1-Bd}{pd} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where Bd=Bulk density

Pd=particle density (2.65g/ cm³)

Moisture content of the soil was determined by oven drying at a temperature of 105⁰C and percentage of moisture in soil calculated mathematically as follows:

$$GMC = \frac{W_2-W_3}{W_3-W_1} \times 100 \quad \text{Where } W_1=\text{Weight of the can, } W_2=\text{Weight of wet sample + can, } W_3=\text{Weight of oven dried sample + can}$$

Statistical analysis

Data collected were subjected to Welch's one way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS Statistical package version 9.4. Separation of treatment means was done using turkey test.

Results and Discussion

Pre-Treatment Soil Properties

The results of soil physical properties of the experimental site before the application of treatment are shown in table 1. From the results obtained, the study area had a mean sand, silt and clay contents of 704 g/kg, 216 g/kg and 80 g/kg respectively, having a textural class of sandy loam. The soils of the study area had a mean bulk density of 1.54 g/ cm³, total porosity of 41.77 %, soil moisture content of 9.67 %, hydraulic conductivity of 0.18 cm/hr and aggregate stability of 0.45%.

Table. 1. Soil Pretreatment properties of the Experimental site.

Soil Parameters	Values
Sand (g/kg)	704
Silt (g/kg)	216
Clay (g/kg)	80
Textural class	Sandy loam
Bulk density (g/ cm ³)	1.54
Porosity (%)	41.77
Aggregate stability (%)	0.45
Moisture content (%)	9.67
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/hr)	0.18

Nutrient Properties of swine wastes

Prior to the treatment application (Swine wastes), it was subjected to laboratory analysis to determine the constituent elements and the results are shown in table 2.

Table. 2. *Nutrient composition of swine waste*

Swine waste properties	values
Organic matter	3.71 %
Total Nitrogen	3.21 %
Available Phosphorus	1.68 mg/kg

Post-Treatment Soil Properties

From the results obtained as shown in table 3, the plot with zero application had an average sand, silt and clay contents of 729 g/kg, 206 g/kg and 65 g/kg respectively, the plot treated with 4.5 kg/plot of swine waste had an average sand, silt and clay contents of 719 g/kg, 201 g/kg and 81 g/kg respectively, the plot treated with 9.0 kg/plot of swine waste had an average sand, silt and clay contents of 719 g/kg, 200 g/kg and 81 g/kg respectively while the plot that was treated with 13.5 kg/plot of swine waste had an average sand, silt and clay contents of 749 g/kg, 175 g/kg and 95 g/kg respectively. The results showed that there was no treatment effect on the texture of the soil; however the sandiness of the studied area could be attributed to the nature of the parent material from which the soils were derived. Soils of the experimental area belongs to textural class of sandy loam. Higher sand contents obtained in soils of the studied area could suggest low cation exchange capacity, leaching of nutrients and can encourage soil erodibility on exposure to high rainfall (Nwosu et al., 2023). The plot with zero treatment (control) had a mean soil bulk density of 1.97g/ cm³, the plot with treatment applied at the rate of 4.5 kg/plot and 9.0 kg/plot had mean soil bulk densities of 1.86 g/ cm³ and 1.75 g/ cm³ respectively while the plot with the treatment applied at the rate of 13.5 kg/ ha had a mean soil bulk density of 1.89 g/ cm³. There was a significant difference in the soil bulk densities when the plot with zero treatment was compared with the plot of 9.0 kg of swine wastes. Bulk density reduces with the application of animal manures; this is because the organic matter has a lower particle density than the mineral particles and its increase results in reduction of the soil particulate density as a whole. Again, increase in soil organic matter increases the degree of soil aggregation, increasing the volume of pores. Soil bulk density as observed in this study was slightly higher than normal and could be attributed to soil compaction owing to machinery compression in the course of road construction around the experimental site. According to Celik et al., 2004; Barzegar et al., 2002, Bulluck et al., 2002 reduction in soil bulk density occurs both with the application of manures alone and in association with mineral fertilizers (Hati et al., 2008; Bandyopadhyay et al., 2010). The plot with zero treatment (control) and 4.5 kg/plot of swine wastes had an average mean total porosities of 25.72 % and 28.91 % respectively, while the plots treated with 9.0 kg/plot and 13.5 kg/plot of swine wastes had a mean total porosities of 23.59 % and 29.59 % respectively. The plot with 13.5 kg/plot had the highest total porosity of 29.79 % while the plot treated

with 9.0kg/plot of swine wastes had the least total porosity of 23.59 %. The results obtained in several studies with application of manure presented divergent results regarding their effects on the total porosity and the classes of pores. Increase in total porosity as often observed is due to the increase of pores with larger diameter ie macropores which is associated with better soil structure (Celik *et al.*, 2004; Rós *et al.*, 2013). Marinari *et al.*, (2000) observed that the increase of macropores in the soil treated with organic fertilizer was mainly due to an increase in the elongated pores which are considered very important for both soil-water plant relationships and maintenance of good soil structure. For aggregate stability; the results showed that the plot with zero treatment had 0.3 %, the plot with 4.5 kg/plot had a mean aggregate stability of 0.44 % while the plot treated at the rates of 9.0 kg/plot and 13.5 kg/plot had a mean aggregate stability of 0.40 % and 0.37 % respectively. The plot with 4.5 kg/plot of swine wastes had the highest aggregate stability with a mean value of 0.44 % while the control and 13.5 kg/plot had 0.37 % mean values respectively being the least. Soil aggregate stability is one of the properties most influenced by increase in manure application however swine wastes application at the rate of 13.5 kg/plot did not increase the aggregate stability and could be as a result of the short period of the experiment. According to Kay *et al.*,(1999) , a level of soil organic carbon of 2.0 to 2.5% is considered necessary to maintain good aggregate stability and aggregate stability is considered to deteriorate rapidly when soil organic carbon falls below 1.2% to 1.5%. Again, the results obtained showed that the plot with zero treatment (control) had a mean hydraulic conductivity of 0.02 cm/hr, the plot with swine waste 4.5 kg/plot had a mean hydraulic conductivity of 0.01 cm/hr, the plot with 9.0 kg/plot had a mean hydraulic conductivity of 0.03 cm/hr while the plot with 13.5 kg/plot had a mean hydraulic conductivity of 0.05 cm/hr. The plot with 13.5 kg/plot had the highest mean value of 0.05 cm/hr while the plot with 4.5 kg/plot had the least mean value of 0.01 cm/hr.

Table. 3. *Influence of application rates of swine wastes on selected Soil Physical Properties*

TRTs	BD (g/cm ³)	TP (%)	MC (%)	Aggregate Stability	Ksat (cm/hr)	Sand (g/kg)	Silt (g/kg)	Clay (g/kg)	Textural class
0 kg/plot	1.97 ^a	25.72 ^b	1.95 ^c	0.37 ^a	0.02 ^a	729	206	65	SL
4.5 kg/plot	1.86 ^{ab}	28.91 ^{ab}	2.26 ^{bc}	0.44 ^a	0.01 ^a	719	201	81	SL
9.0 kg/plot	1.75 ^b	23.59 ^a	3.22 ^a	0.40 ^a	0.03 ^a	719	200	81	SL
13.5 kg/plot	1.89 ^{ab}	29.59 ^{ab}	2.97 ^{ab}	0.37 ^a	0.05 ^{ab}	749	175	76	SL

Note: TRTs- Treatments BD –Bulk density TP - Total porosity MC-moisture content
Ksat – saturated hydraulic Conductivity

There was a significant difference in soil hydraulic conductivity when plot treated with 13.5kg of swine wastes was compared with the control. Some researchers have reported seepage reduction due to sealing of soils by animal manure and by other organic liquids which

was observed in this study. In their submission, organic manure is known to improve soil physical properties (Andersodu et al., 2013, Aluko and Oyeleke, (2005).

Agronomic properties

Some agronomic properties such as plant height, leaf area index and number of leaves, Fresh shoot weight, dry shoot weight, number of nodes at first and second cuts were taken 3weeks after transplanting to determine the influence of swine wastes application rates on the Amaranthus plant.

Plant Height

From the results obtained, the plots with 0kg, 4.5 kg/plot, 9.0 kg/plot, and 13.5 kg/plot rates of swine waste application had a mean plant height of 37.25 cm, 39.65 cm, 44.90 cm, and 49.95 cm respectively. Highest height was observed in the plot treated with 13.5 kg/plot of swine waste while the lowest height was observed in the plot with zero treatment. Giacomini and Aita (2008) revealed that animal waste such as deep litter and liquid pig slurry applied as a source of N for corn increased the availability of this nutrient in the soil throughout the crop cycle compared to the control treatment.

Leaf area index and number of leaves

The plots with zero treatment had a mean leaf area index and number of leaves of 37.60 cm and 43.15 cm respectively, the plot treated with 4.5 kg/plot of swine waste had a mean leaf area index of 46.50 cm and 60.90 cm respectively, the plot treated with 9.0 kg/plot of swine waste had a mean leaf area index of 43.47 cm and 73.00 cm respectively while the plot treated with 13.5 kg/plot of swine waste had a mean leaf area index of 70.80 cm and 73.90 cm respectively. There was a significant difference at 5% probability level in the leaf area index when the plots with 0kg/plot,4.5kg/plot, 9.0kg/plot swine waste application were compared with 13.5kg/plot swine waste application. Leaves are the main source of food synthesized for the plant and thus their absence affects plant growth and development thus Leaf area is recognized as a crucial growth index determining the capacity of plants to trap solar energy for photosynthesis and has marked effect on growth and yield of plant (Mathowa et al., 2014)

Table. 4. *Influence of application rates of swine wastes on some agronomic properties*

TRTs	Plant Height	Leaf area index	Number of leaves	FSW (kg)	DSW (kg)	NODES (1ST CUT)	NODES (2ND CUT)
0kg/plot	37.25 ^a	37.60 ^a	43.15 ^a	0.51 ^a	0.15 ^a	13.85 ^a	4.80 ^a
4.5kg/plot	39.65 ^{ab}	46.50 ^a	60.90 ^{ab}	0.32 ^a	0.15 ^{ab}	14.75 ^b	5.85 ^a
9.0kg/plot	44.90 ^b	43.40 ^a	73.00 ^b	0.47 ^a	0.12 ^b	14.50 ^b	4.75 ^b
13.5kg/plot	49.95 ^{bc}	70.80 ^b	73.90 ^b	0.51 ^a	0.17 ^c	13.10 ^b	4.75 ^b

N/B: FSW =fresh shoot weight, DSW=Dry shoot weight

Fresh shoot weight, Dry shoot weight, Number of nodes at first and second cut.

The plot treated with 13.5 kg/plot of swine waste gave the highest dry shoot weight of 0.17kg, while the plot treated with 9.0 kg/plot of swine waste had the lowest weight of 0.12kg. Nodes were more at the first cut than in the second cut at various application rates however there was a significant difference in the nodes at the first cut when plots with 4.5 kg/plot, 9.0 kg/plot and 13.5 kg/plot were compared with zero application. Generally, it was observed that plant height, leaf area index, number of leaves, fresh shoot and dry shoot weight increased with an increase in treatment application rates. This could be attributed to high content of Total N, P and K in the pig manure. Adebayo et al (2011) found out that organic amendment increased both vegetative and dry matter yield of *Moringa oleifera*.

Conclusion

The application of swine wastes at different rates had an appreciable impact on some soil physical properties such as the soil bulk density, total porosity and moisture content. The research showed that the higher the rate of swine wastes application for cultivation of Amaranthus the better the growth and yield which was evidenced in the plant height, leaf area index, number of leaves as well as fresh and dry shoot weights measured.

Recommendation

Farmers growing annual crops with short growth cycle such as Amaranthus should use swine wastes at rate of 9kg/plot and above to obtain relative higher yields.

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